

#BelBi2024 • Belgrade, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

5th Belgrade Bioinformatics Conference

17 - 20 JUNE 2024

EDITORS

Dr. Ivana Morić

Dr. Valentina Đorđević

ISBN: 978-86-82679-16-5

belbi.bg.ac.rs

Title	5 th Belgrade Bioinformatics Conference BOOK OF ABSTRACTS
Publisher	Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, University of Belgrade Vojvode Stepe 444a, Belgrade, Serbia https://www.imgge.bg.ac.rs/
Editors	dr. Ivana Morić dr. Valentina Đorđević
Technical editor	dr. Dušan Radojević
ISBN	978-86-82679-16-5
Copyright	© 2024 Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, University of Belgrade

BelBi2024 Committees

International Advisory Board

Alessandro Treves,
International School for Advanced Studies,
Trieste, Italy

Elena Fimmel
Mannheim University of Applied Sciences,
Mannheim, Germany

Guanglan Zhang,
Boston University, Boston, USA

Konstantin Severinov,
Waksman Institute for Microbiology,
Rutgers University, New Jersey, USA

Lou Chitkushev,
Metropolitan College, Boston University,
Boston, USA

Oxana Galzitskaya,
Institute of Protein Research,
Russian Academy of Sciences,
Moscow, Russia

Paul Sorba,
Laboratory of Theoretical Physics and CNRS,
Annecy, France

Predrag Radivojac,
Khoury College of Computer Sciences,
Northeastern University, Boston, USA

Vladimir Brusić,
Li Dak Sum Chair Professor of Computer Science,
University of Nottingham, Ningbo, China

Vladimir Uversky,
Department of Molecular Medicine,
University of South Florida, Tampa, USA

Yuriy Orlov,
I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical
University, Moscow, Russia

Zoran Ognjanović,
Mathematical Institute, Serbian Academy
of Sciences and Arts, Belgrade, Serbia

International Program Committee

Alexandre de Brevern,
INSERM, Université Paris Cité, Université
de la Réunion, Paris, France

Biljana Stanković,
Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic
Engineering, University of Belgrade, Serbia

Branislava Gemović,
VINCA Institute of Nuclear Sciences,
University of Belgrade, Serbia

Branko Dragovich,
Mathematical Institute, Serbian Academy of
Sciences and Arts, Belgrade, Serbia

Dragan Matić,
Faculty of Sciences, Department of Mathe-
matics and Informatics, University of Banja
Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Fotis Psomopoulos,
Centre for Research and Technology Hellas,
Thessaloniki, Greece

Hong-Yu OU,
Shanghai Jiao Tong University, The Microbial
Bioinformatics Group, State Key Laboratory
of Microbial Metabolism, Shanghai, China

Ivana Morić,
Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic
Engineering, University of Belgrade, Serbia

Ivana Strahinić,
Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic
Engineering, University of Belgrade, Serbia

Marko Đorđević,
Faculty of Biology,
University of Belgrade, Serbia

Nataša Pržulj,
Catalan Institution for Research and
Advanced Studies (ICREA), Spain;
Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Spain;
University College London, UK

Nenad Mitić,
Faculty of Mathematics,
University of Belgrade, Serbia

Peter Tompa,
VIB Structural Biology Research Center,
Brussels

Saša Malkov,
Faculty of Mathematics,
University of Belgrade, Serbia

Sergei Kozyrev,
Department of Mathematical Physics,
Steklov Mathematical Institute RAS,
Moscow, Russia

Valentina Đorđević,
Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic
Engineering, University of Belgrade, Serbia

Vladimir Babenko,
Institute of Cytology and Genetics,
Novosibirsk, Russia

Local Organizing Committee

Anđela Rodić,
Faculty of Biology,
University of Belgrade

Marko Đorđević,
Faculty of Biology,
University of Belgrade

Gordana Pavlović-Lazetić,
Faculty of Mathematics,
University of Belgrade

Jovana Kovačević,
Faculty of Mathematics,
University of Belgrade

Nenad Mitić,
Faculty of Mathematics,
University of Belgrade

Saša Malkov,
Faculty of Mathematics,
University of Belgrade

Željko D. Popović,
Faculty of Sciences,
University of Novi Sad

Branko Dragovich,
Mathematical Institute, Serbian Academy
of Sciences and Arts, Belgrade

Branislava Gemović,
VINCA Institute of Nuclear Sciences,
University of Belgrade

Tanja Vukov,
Institute for Biological Research "Siniša
Stanković", University of Belgrade, Belgrade

Dušan Radojević,
Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic
Engineering, University of Belgrade

Ivana Morić,
Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic
Engineering, University of Belgrade

Nikola Kotur,
Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic
Engineering, University of Belgrade

Valentina Đorđević,
Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic
Engineering, University of Belgrade

ORGANIZER

Institute of Molecular Genetics
and Genetic Engineering,
University of Belgrade

MAIN CO-ORGANIZERS

Faculty of Mathematics,
University of Belgrade

Mathematical Institute
of SASA,
Belgrade

Faculty of Biology,
University of Belgrade

Vinča Institute of
Nuclear Sciences,
University of Belgrade

Serbian Society for Bioinformatics
and Computational Biology

CO-ORGANIZERS

Institute for Biological
Research "Siniša Stanković",
University of Belgrade

Institute for Medical
Research,
University in Belgrade

Faculty of Sciences,
University of Novi Sad

BioIRC - Bioengineering
Research and
Development Center

Faculty of Engineering,
University of Kragujevac

C4IR Serbia

Centre for the Fourth
Industrial Revolution
in Serbia

Serbian Society for
Molecular Biology

Serbian Society for
Microbiology

Biophysical Society
of Serbia

Center for the
Promotion of Science

Navigating ELSI for FAIR multiomics data management within STEPUPIORS international rectal cancer project

Miljana Tanić¹, Mariska Bierkens², Marko Radulović¹, Aleksandra Stanojević¹, Mladen Marinković³, Ana Krivokuća¹, Radmila Janković¹, Ana Đurić¹, Sergi Castellvi-Bel⁴, Jerome Zoidakis^{5,6}, Remond J. Fijneman² and Milena Čavić¹

¹ Experimental Oncology Department, Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia (IORS), Belgrade, Serbia

² Department of Pathology, Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI), Amsterdam, Netherlands

³ Department of Radiation Oncology, Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

⁴ Gastroenterology Department, Fundació Recerca Clínic Barcelona-Institut d'Investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi i Sunyer (FRCB-IDIBAPS), Barcelona, Spain

⁵ Department of Biotechnology, Biomedical Research Foundation, Academy of Athens (BRFAA), Athens, Greece.

⁶ Department of Biology, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, Greece

tanic.miljana@ncrc.ac.rs

The STEPUPIORS project entails a multi-omics approach to studying neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy (nCRT) response in locally-advanced rectal cancer (LARC) patients through retrospective and prospective longitudinal sample and data collection. Through a multinational collaboration including four partnering institutions (IORS - Serbia, NKI - Netherlands, BRFAA - Greece, FRCB-IDIBAPS - Spain) different layers of omics data are being generated and integrated to derive biomarkers and models for prediction of patient's response to nCRT. Consideration of Ethical, legal and societal issues (ELSI) is mandatory for projects dealing with personal and sensitive data, and collection of biological material from patients. The international nature of the project necessitates compliance with both national (Serbian) and EU laws and regulatory provisions governing data privacy and patient protection.

Ethics approvals were sought with the IORS' local Committee for retrospective use of samples and health records, and for prospective collection and biobanking of samples and associated metadata, supplying patient information sheet and 2-tiered informed consent form. Prospectively collected samples and data will be managed by a Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) acquired within the newly established IORS Biobank. International collaboration was facilitated through signing of Consortium and Joint controller agreements specifying terms for transfer of material including data, non-disclosure of information and data processing activities.

A Data Management Plan (DMP) was made considering a wide range of data types including structured information from patients' medical records, radiology images, genomics, transcriptomics and proteomics data. DMP contained detailed descriptions of type of processing, source of data, data format and quantity. Means of maintaining confidentiality were described, which include access control, pseudonymization, separate processing of data collected for different purposes. Free access to data was achieved through deposition of raw data in appropriate repositories (Zenodo, EGA, cBioPortal) and as Supplementary data

Flash talks

in open access publications in accordance with EU's Open Science policy and in line with Findable, Accessible, Interoperable Research data (FAIR) principles.

Here we provide the roadmap and examples for navigating the complex ELSI landscape required for FAIR biomedical and multi-omics data management in accordance with the applicable regulatory provisions relating to the protection of the personal data and to medical confidentiality.

Keywords: data management, regulatory, ethics, privacy, omics

Acknowledgement: Horizon Europe Project STEPUPIORS (101079217)